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Review of “An FFT solver used for virtual Dynamic Mechanical Analysis experiments: Application to a glassy/amorphous system and to a particulate composite”

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1 Reviewer #1 (F. Willot)

Reviewer

This work centers on the effective viscous response of two heterogeneous materials previously studied in the literature. Making use of an FFT-based method for this type of problems, the authors interpret previous experimental data and FEM results that they confront to FFT predictions. They obtain original results and the article is well written and contains relevant references, therefore I suggest that the manuscript be accepted for publication provided the following remarks are addressed.

The authors make use of an FFT-based algorithm to solve the linear viscoelasticity problem in a heterogeneous material in the harmonic regime. The numerical scheme is based on the extension of FFT methods for linear elasticity with complex elastic moduli for the phases in the Laplace-Carson domain (work of Figliuzzi et al). Both the Green operators associated to the strain and stress problems are used to overcome well-known convergence difficulties associated with strongly-contrasted phases (works of Monchiet and of Da Silva and Moulinec). The convergence criterion involves both the strain compatibility and stress equilibrium which are not guaranteed (except upon convergence) with this scheme.

The numerical scheme is validated on a checkerboard microstructure which as a 2D autodial material admits an exact solution in terms of effective properties (geometric mean). The results are convincing, since the checkerboard structure is especially singular (in particular the existence of a pole at 0 for the square-root function in the complex plane). A 2-term Prony series is proposed to model the effective response.

The numerical tool is used to simulate the behavior of an amorphous “pixel”-material with glassy and rubber elastic constants (studied by Masurel et al 2015 [DOI]). Comparisons are made with rheological models. Did the authors try to perform a data collapse on the data of Fig. 3, making use of the asymptotic behavior at high-contrast (G' or G'' proportional to ω^2 and ω)?

Authors

Maybe we don't exactly understand the question and will answer evasively then. The reason for adding the asymptotic behavior of G' and G'' for high contrasts (linear behavior in ω^2 and ω , respectively) was precisely to show that both simulations (FEM approach of Masurel and coll.

and present virtual DMA approach) produce data collapsing asymptotically to the expected linear behavior (in log scale). For $G_g/G_r = 10^7$ i.e. when the relaxed state vanishes (the SLS model degenerates to the pure Maxwell element or sometimes called Debye model), it is well known that we then have a ω^2 behavior at low frequencies (Jonscher A.K., Universal Relaxation Law. London: Chelsea Dielectrics Press. 1996, p. 415, ISBN 0-9508711-2-5). Of course here, as a result of the academic purpose, the model is still Standard Linear Solid but as the range of investigated frequencies is unlimited (which would not be possible in real life due to inertial effects at high frequencies and too short life (!) at low frequencies), this behavior appears as in the low frequency band below $\omega\tau_{\max} = 1$. Because the modelling assumes the existence of a relaxed modulus (even infinitely small) there will always be a frequency which will produce a departure from the linear regime to produce a constant plateau. In Figure 1 we plot this behavior when the distribution of times is cancelled and only one single relaxation time is considered and set to $\tau_{\max} = 1$ s (Curve labelled “SLS model”). This corresponds to the case where all voxels of Fig. 2(b) are made of the same viscoelastic material with $G_r = 10^{-7}$. As can be seen the perfect plateau is observed for frequencies below $\omega\tau_{\max} < 10^{-5}$. But for investigated frequencies such that $10^{-4} < \omega\tau_{\max} < 10^{-1}$, the behavior follows the ω^2 trend. In the second figure, we adopt the normalized plot of Jonscher which makes this more evident.

Of course, in the results presented in the paper, the relaxation times are distributed around τ_{\max} which makes curves $G_g/G_r = 10^{-7}$ to depart from curve “SLS model” (with a single $\tau = \tau_{\max}$).

Reviewer A polystyrene/glass composite is considered in Sec. 3.2. Referring to Fig. 6, the authors write:

“Note that experimental data (full circles) nevertheless depart substantially from the matrix data which may suggest that some bias is present in the experiments.”

It is difficult to attribute the experimentally-observed difference in the effective properties between $f_v = 0$ (matrix) and $f_v = 6\%$ to any bias in the experiment, as many physical phenomena may occur (e.g. the role of interfaces or micro-porosities or any other ingredient not taken into account in the FFT computations).

Authors Yes, this is exactly what we had in mind. One should rather speak of a bias related to the mismatch between the ideal character of the models and the reality of the experimental conditions, here mainly due to – we fully agree – the composite specimen which is not perfectly known (porosity, aggregation, distribution of sizes not given, interphases?) and therefore not included in the simulations (but it could be possible). It is well known that GSC or other effective models generally confirm that the effective behavior at low volume fraction is very close to the matrix behavior (but with the same idealized conditions). In Fig. 6 however, it can be seen that the experimental data points and theoretical curves depart essentially in the transition zone. They match rather perfectly in the low and high temperature range. That’s maybe why it can be considered that a bias may be due to the experiment itself. The data points are given in intrinsic variable (the Young modulus) but these data come from a conversion of overall stiffness measurements which generally depend on specimen size, stability of the loading conditions through grips, temperature delay in the sweep mode... There are many reasons then to obtain rather biased data. Note that the virtual DMA tool offers by the way an opportunity to investigate their reality.

We change the sentence to put forward the mismatch between experiments and theoretical simulations.

Reviewer I’d suggest that the authors include the Christensen and Lo or other relevant prediction of linear homogenization theories (e.g. Hervé/Zaoui) in Fig. 6. The reference to Christensen and Lo’s paper is missing.

Authors The reference Christensen and Lo has been added. The Christensen and Lo GSC 2-phase and Hervé and Zaoui 4-phase model predictions were used by Agbossou et al. (1993) and Alberola and Mele (1996) as explained in the paper. They do not result in good predictions when compared to the experimental data when virtual DMA does. We added in Figs. 5(a,b) (new numbering) the

Figure 1 Behavior of the material for a single relaxation time $\tau_{max} = 1$ s

Christensen and Lo predictions at a 50 % volume fraction and refer to this curve in the text. Note that these predictions are quasi insensitive to the Poisson’s ratio.

Reviewer Also, the authors may want to emphasize when they refer to *generalized* self-consistent estimates rather than the classical self-consistent estimate originally developed by Bruggeman and Kerner.

Authors OK, modifications made accordingly in the text.

Reviewer Two other points might be addressed or clarified in the manuscript and to this reviewer:
Point 1. Clarification of the justification for the FFT/experimental difference in Fig. 6. Although the authors demonstrate that the effective response is sensitive to the Poisson’s ratio in the matrix, do they claim that the differences between FFT results and experimental data in Fig. 6 is to be explained by the same Poisson’s ratio (and its variation if any w.r.t. frequency)?

Authors No, we do not claim that. This attempt to explain Alberola and coll. results with DMA simulations takes all its interest here in this section in view of two points: (i) there is an extreme sensitivity of the results to the matrix Poisson’s ratio and (ii) there is no need to invoke a complex variable for the Poisson’s ratio to explain the data. We just show that a Poisson’s coefficient assumed to be real and constant with a value close to incompressibility (a rather realistic option for a polymer in the transition regime) is the best to explain the observed data. The following section (see our answer to the next comment) pushes the reflection a little further by considering that it may also be dependent on the temperature (an obvious reality also) which again makes the simulation results evolve. All experiments were performed at a constant frequency and generally a DMA apparatus sets this frequency precisely. Here, the addressed question was relative to a correct interpretation or understanding of the data in a given temperature range (another strong advantage of this virtual DMA tool, able to work with tabulated temperature data properties of the constituents).

Reviewer **Point 2.** Fig. 7 in the last section presents results for “different” particle size. As far as I understand, the homogenized properties predicted by the FFT computations can not depend on scale, unless the particle size influences their dispersion or the phase local properties (which is not the case here, as far as I know).

Authors Absolutely. This is precisely one of the questions raised by the apparent contradiction between Virtual DMA and the experimental data of Alberola et al. This section and associated figure show how extreme is the sensitivity to the Poisson’s ratio of the matrix. If the complex nature of the Poisson’s ratio cannot be invoked (proof given in the preceding section), we investigate here the thermal dependence of the Poisson’s coefficient (which is obvious in reality). It is then shown that the contradiction could be removed. Because the sensitivity of the results is strong when the behavior tends to the incompressibility limit, the temperature dependence of the properties is crucial. This may suggest for example that the two different distributions change the thermal conductivity responsible of the thermal regime of the specimen in a sweeping process. Obviously it is impossible to know, especially because experimental data are not ours. That’s why our conclusion consists in showing how helpful this simulation tool could be to raise conceptual difficulties and/or, search for a rationale to explain data, question the data (experimental bias) and/or, open new investigation ideas.

Reviewer Could the authors also indicate the microstructure model used for the FFT computations in Sec. 3.2.3. Fig. 8 suggest the use of a RSA model in 3D (with constant radius?).

Authors We gave a few explanations in the preliminaries of Section 3.2.3. Yes, we use RSA and RSA+Metropolis algorithm for high volume fractions. The radius of particles is not constant as we have to simulate distribution of sizes d_1 and d_2 corresponding to those characterized experimentally. All details are provided below.

Figure 2 Normal radius distributions (on the left) and corresponding 3D dispersions in a $1 \times 1 \times 1$ box (on the right) for two different ratios R_{\max}/R_{\min} at the same volume fraction $V_f = 0.5$ and a given error $\alpha = 1.25\%$. Top: $R_{\max}/R_{\min} = 110/70$; bottom: $R_{\max}/R_{\min} = 45/1$.

Squared box filled with spheres following normal distribution of radius: building procedure. In the first step normal distributions (see Figure 2 left) of radius are built respecting the following conditions and parameters:

$$\frac{R - \langle R \rangle}{\sigma} \sim N(0, 1) \quad (\text{normal})$$

$$P_N(R \in [R_{\min}, R_{\max}]) = 1 - \alpha \quad (\text{proba})$$

A given error α leads to a standard deviation

$$\sigma = \frac{R_{\max} - R_{\min}}{2q_{\alpha/2}},$$

where $q_{\alpha/2}$ is the quantile of the reduced normal centered law $N(0, 1)$ for an error $\alpha/2$. For a chosen ratio, R_{\max}/R_{\min} and a chosen volume fraction V_f , the average radius $(R_{\max} + R_{\min})/2$ and the number of spheres N are adjusted to fit in a square box of dimensions $1 \times 1 \times 1$. In order to build spheres dispersions for our simulation boxes we used a Random Sequential Adsorption (RSA) algorithm or Metropolis algorithm in the case of the largest volume fractions. We will describe both algorithms below.

During our RSA process, spherical particles are randomly introduced in a squared box of dimensions $1 \times 1 \times 1$. Once a sphere is placed, it cannot be removed. When an attempt to deposit an additional sphere would result in an overlap with one or more already deposited spheres, this attempt is rejected. In our case spheres are introduced following the normal distribution (proba) starting from the largest ones ending with the smallest ones. The total overlap in the box is calculated with the following expression:

$$Overlap = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=i+1}^N \max \{0, R_i + R_j - \|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j\| - \text{tolerance}\} \quad (\text{overlap}),$$

where N is the total number of spherical particles in the box, R_i and R_j are radius of particles i and j respectively, $\|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j\|$ represent the Euclidean distance between particles i and j , and $\text{tolerance} = 0$. Total *Overlap* during the entire procedure should be 0. Using this algorithm, for small volume fraction such as $V_f = 0.06$, gives a complete 3D dispersion very quickly. However, in cases of large volume fractions such as $V_f = 0.5$ this simple process gives final results in very long computer times. In order to accelerate the process, the RSA algorithm is modified in order to accept small overlaps between spheres ($\text{tolerance} > 0$ and $Overlap = 0$) at first. Once the entire distribution of spheres is disposed into the box, the spheres are moved following a metropolis algorithm in order to lead to no overlap ($\text{tolerance} = 0$ and $Overlap = 0$) at the end. At iteration p total overlap $Overlap_p$ is calculated. At iteration p' the Metropolis algorithm selects randomly one of the N spheres and attempt to move it in a random direction from a random distance below a fixed value $\|\mathbf{r}_i^{p'} - \mathbf{r}_i^p\| < d_{\max}$. A probability ratio is calculated between positions $\mathbf{r}_i^{p'}$ and \mathbf{r}_i^p as follow:

$$a = \frac{Overlap_p}{Overlap_{p'}} \quad (\text{overlap})$$

If $a \geq 1$, we take $\mathbf{r}_i^{p+1} = \mathbf{r}_i^{p'}$, otherwise if $a < 1$, we take $\mathbf{r}_i^{p+1} = \mathbf{r}_i^p$ with probability $1 - a$. The Metropolis algorithm runs until $Overlap = 0$ (with $\text{tolerance} = 0$).

2 Reviewer #2 (Anonymous)

Reviewer

This article is a numerical study of the steady-state harmonic response of linear viscoelastic composites using a Fast-Fourier transform numerical solver. It relies classically on the use of the correspondence principle which leads to a symbolic elastic heterogeneous problem with complex moduli. It has been implemented by the authors in the CraFT software initially developed by H. Moulinec and P. Suquet. This approach is not new but its implementation in a freely distributed

software can be useful to promote its use in the scientific community. The authors first present a numerical validation with an analytical result (checkerboard microstructure made of standard linear solid materials), then FFT simulations are used to revisit previously published results, either numerical or experimental. This choice of the authors makes this article rather unusual but not without interest. However, since no new numerical or theoretical approaches are proposed and published experimental results are used, I suggest that the article be significantly shortened and focused on three points:

- (i) the CraFT implementation,
- (ii) the critical analysis of different physical models (Section 3.1.3) and
- (iii) the discussion of experimental results on polystyrene/glass beads composites in the light of new FFT-based unit-cell simulations (Section 3.2).

Authors We follow the advice of reducing substantially the article. Regarding points

- (i) We do our best to maintain the general view of the key equations of the classical FFT approach but suppress many intermediate steps (number of equations initially 20 reduced to 8). We add some information about the way it was implemented in CraFT (request formulated in the Detailed comments)
- (ii) Section 3.1, we remove a half-page introducing the problem in Section 3.1. This option was a little bit tricky because the presentation of the case “pixel amorphous” (quoting Reviewer #1 (F. Willot)) contains many elements providing the counterpoints necessary to defend the intrinsic superiority of the virtual DMA. But we consider that this shortening favors to go more directly – and therefore stress – the key point of obtaining the frequency modulus with no additional treatment. We also removed the part relative to the confrontation of both FEM and present FFT approach in terms of the local fields (another half-page). Depending on JTCAM editorial policies and/or editor decision, it may be possible to consider this part as Supplementary Information? Indeed, from our point of view, this result is an opportunity to show the reader that the spectral approach’s characteristic, offering reduced computational times, gains greater interest as it is possible with low developments and in the same tool to go from virtual DMA simulations in complex variables to temporal simulations with time-dependent variables. DMA apparatus generally offer the possibility to perform DMA experiments and relaxation or creep experiments. It is possible to imagine then to chain CraFT computations both in harmonic complex and temporal modes in an inverse approach of identifying material parameters from both experiments. This would be undoubtedly a precious opportunity.

We add this information in a Supplementary Information file in case this option is retained. [*This part was moved to the appendix* (L. Brassart)]

Reviewer Here are some more specific comments that also deserve to be addressed before this article can be considered for publication:

- In the introduction, it is suggested that imperfect interfaces cannot be handled (continuity assumptions between particles and matrix). This question has been addressed in the context of FFT methods (see, for instance, V. Monchiet, *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, 135, 14-25, 2018 [DOI]).

Authors The sentence has been modified to nuance this point and the reference to Monchiet paper has been added.

Reviewer The details on the classical numerical aspects of the FFT method could be removed and Section 2 should be more focused on the CraFT development. The reference (Suquet, 2012 [DOI]) for the correspondence principle is not very relevant. I suggest to write “elastic classical scheme” instead of “temporal classical scheme”.

Authors The suggestions have been considered and the text modified accordingly (see supra).

Reviewer The reference (Gélébart and Ouaki, 2015 [DOI]) should be more correctly cited since it also proposes a procedure of composite voxels.

- Authors** Yes, two numerical drawbacks of the approach are connected: spurious oscillations at interfaces and precision/consistency of the results when “complex” materials are considered in terms of interfaces between the constituents. On the basis of our reading of the two cited papers from Gélébart (Gélébart and Ouaki, 2015 [DOI]; Charière et al., 2020 [DOI]) and the choice made by the authors for the title of their article, we reproduced this distinction. Indeed, the composite voxels are used in the former with the objective of filtering spurious oscillations (initial purpose of the method) whereas the latter presents the resorts to composite voxels to consider Gas/Glass/Matrix interfaces in the case of syntactic foams (hollow glass microspheres in a matrix). We modify the text to put forward the composite voxel approach as a proposition to solve both drawbacks.
- Reviewer** In the results of the numerical validation (checkerboard) reported in Table 1, the term “Effective exact SLS” is misleading since it suggests that the effective behavior is SLS, that is a Zener model. This is clearly not the case as it can be seen in Figure 1. It has been shown theoretically that a mixture of Zener constituents is not described in general by a Zener model (Gallican, Brenner and Suquet, C.R. Mécanique, 2017 [DOI]).
- Authors** Absolutely. Inappropriate shortcut in the labeling of the effective modulus. Notation refers originally to “effective exact for a medium made of two SLS constituents”. We change for “Effective exact \tilde{G} Eq. (11)” to avoid any confusion. Reference to (Gallican, Brenner and Suquet, C. R. Mécanique, 2017 [DOI]) added with an appropriate comment.
- Reviewer** Concerning the discussion on the frequency shift of the damping peak, it must be mentioned that in the case of rigid or porous inclusions in an incompressible matrix, the effective $\tan \delta$ peak is exactly the one of the matrix (see, Z. Hashin, Int. J. Solids Struct., 6, p. 546, 1970 [DOI]).
- Authors** Two-folded answer:
- a/ There is no discussion relative to a *frequency* shift of $\tan \delta$ but to a temperature shift. The scientists who perform DMA experiments on this particulate composite report a slight shift of $\tan \delta$ w.r.t. the temperature. This is not confirmed by virtual DMA simulations and therefore suggests the existence of some experimental bias.
 - b/ Anyway, this absence of temperature shift is in line with the idea that the peak is entirely ruled by the matrix. But cannot be related to the conclusions of (Hashin, 1970 [DOI]) from our point of view. Indeed, Hashin obtains the result that $(\tan \delta)^{\text{eff}} = (\tan \delta)^{\text{matrix}}$ for a set of assumptions: (i) elastic dilatational and viscoelastic shear behaviors, (ii) a very weak $\tan \delta$ which is obtained for polymers at temperatures far below T_g . (iii) incompressible behavior of the matrix. He never refers to the behavior when $\tan \delta$ is at its maximum. Our computations, accompanying the experimental data obtained by Alberola and coll., are obtained without complying with (i), (ii) and the case (iii) is considered when studying the sensitivity to the Poisson’s ratio to discuss the data. It is clear that the key interest here through DMA simulations is to capture the behavior within the vitreous state (i.e. above the glass transition of PS which is about $T_g \cong 100$ °C). Far below it is observed that the $\tan \delta$ is obviously low (it couldn’t be different) and that the matrix and composite behavior do not exhibit differences hence $(\tan \delta)^{\text{eff}} = (\tan \delta)^{\text{matrix}}$ as can be seen in Figure 5-b (but for low temperatures imperatively). We add a short sentence to make this point clearer at the end of Section “Influence of the volume fraction of the particles”.
- In the end, this remark shows the interesting questions open by virtual DMA simulations and the way they could be addressed.

3 Editor’s assessment (L. Brassart)

The paper presents a numerical implementation and validation of a FFT solver for heterogeneous, linear viscoelastic media. The solver operates in the frequency domain, thus directly providing access to effective storage and loss moduli through so-called “virtual DMA” experiments. As pointed out by Reviewer 2 (Anonymous), the approach is not new, however its implementation in the Free Software CraFT and publication of the source code will broadly benefit the community. The second main interest of the paper is the demonstration of how virtual DMA can be used to

analyse (previously-reported) experimental DMA results. Potential benefits of combining virtual and experimental DMA include: parameter identification, assessment of hypotheses regarding microstructure and local properties, and local fields analysis.

Both reviewers asked for a number of clarifications on the first version of the manuscript, as shown above. Reviewer 2 (Anonymous) also asked for a reduction of the paper length to focus on the essential ideas. This Editor further requested for the code to be made available to the community. The authors satisfyingly addressed all the reviewers' comments and both reviewers recommended the paper for publication.